

Active Thin Film Anodes for Alkaline Water Electrolysis^ψ

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Thin films of Co_3O_4 , NiCo_2O_4 , LaNiO_3 , $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ and of Ni-Fe alloys were prepared on conductive supports and their physicochemical and electrocatalytic properties towards oxygen evolution reaction in alkaline medium have been investigated. The electrode kinetic parameters such as, the Tafel slope and the reaction order with respect to OH^- concentration have been determined. Based on the results suitable mechanisms for the oxygen evolution reaction are suggested.

The rapid industrialisation all over the world and the excessive use of coal, petroleum and natural gases (fossil fuels) and technologies for fossil fuels extraction, processing, and particularly their end-use (combustion) have harmful effects on the environment resulting in acid rain, acid dew, acid fog, acid snow, green-house effects etc. These affect adversely the ecological system and also our economy directly or indirectly. In view of these, efforts are being made all over the world to develop pollution-free energy devices based on renewable energy resources, such as bio-mass, wind energy, tidal waves and solar radiations. Of these, solar energy¹ appears to be vary promising one to meet our demands.

Solar and other non-conventional energies like wind have fluctuating characters. It is, therefore, essential to develop convenient methods for energy storage so as to maintain the supply of power without any break. Water electrolysis is presently considered as most convenient method to store electricity in the form of hydrogen, which is a non-pollutant fuel and can be commercially stored and transported without much problems.

In water electrolysis, both acid as well as alkaline solutions can be used as electrolytes. In an alkaline solution most of the electrodes are stable. On contrary, an acid solution involves

corrosion of the electrode materials. Most of commercial electrolyzers use 15–30 w/o KOH as electrolyte, mild steel or nickel as cathode and nickel or plated nickel as anode². The theoretical voltage required to electrolyse water is 1.23 V (vs NHE) at 25°. This voltage decreases by 0.85 mV per degree rise in temperature. Practically, the cell requires a considerably higher voltage than the theoretical one, resulting in a low energy efficiency. So, the commercial production of hydrogen by this method is not economical at present and carried out only in those countries where large quantities of cheap electrical powers such as nuclear (France and Belgium) and hydroelectric powers (Canada, Brazil, Zaire, etc.) are available. Due to high cost of the electricity, this process does not meet more than 1–2% of world's hydrogen demands².

Another important problem with commercial water electrolysis cell is that the nickel anodes show an increase in overpotential with time, the increase being more at higher anodic potentials. The higher practical cell voltage, in fact, arises due to the contribution of the following factors to the overall cell voltage : (i) the reversible potential for anode (E_a) and the reversible potential for cathode (E_c), (ii) the overpotential for hydrogen evolution at the cathode (η_c), (iii) the overpotential for oxygen evolution at the anode (η_a), (iv) ohmic

^ψFr. L. M. Yeddanapalli Memorial Lecture (1991) delivered at the 30th Annual Convention of Chemists, organised under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society, on 22 December 1993 at Calcutta.

drop in the electrolyte, electrode etc., and in any separator in the cell (iR), and (v) any increase in potential with time during operation due to deterioration of the electrode materials (ΔV_t).

Therefore, the overall-cell voltage can be written as

$$\Delta V = E_a - E_c + \eta_a + \eta_c + iR + \Delta V_t$$

Hence, energy efficiency =

$$\frac{\text{Theoretical cell voltage}}{\text{Practical cell voltage}} \\ = (E_a - E_c) / \Delta V$$

Thus, the efficiency of the electrolytic cell would be higher provided the other factors such as, η , iR and ΔV_t are to be minimised by using highly conductive electrode as well as the electrolyte, ΔV_t is related to the stability of the electrode. η_a and η_c can be diminished by developing suitable electrocatalyst.

Investigations have been carried out to increase the efficiency of the traditional nickel anode³⁻⁸ and to develop new electrocatalysts⁹⁻¹² which are active and more economical. The research works were mainly carried out in following directions: (i) to decrease the internal cell resistance, (ii) to improve the efficiency of the traditional electrodes, and (iii) to search for low cost and corrosion stable electrodes of considerably reduced oxygen/hydrogen overpotential. To minimise the internal resistance of the electrolyser, several suitable diaphragms (or membrane) have been developed^{2,13}. With these diaphragms, the inter-electrode distance could be reduced to 1-2 mm. Some of these diaphragms are polymer-reinforced asbestos, sinter nickel, PTFE-bonded zirconia, nickel net-backed porous cermet diaphragms, etc. With these diaphragms it has now been possible to bring down the specific resistance¹ as low as $0.4 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, however, the target is to achieve not more than $0.2 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$. The older cells have specific cell resistance of the order of $1 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$.

Though nickel is unstable under anodic polarisation conditions, effort of minimising of oxygen and hydrogen overpotential is continued on this inexpensive electrode material and also on its

alloys. In view of these, various methods, such as powder coatings³, Raney nickel coatings⁴, electrodeposition⁵⁻⁷, plasma spraying⁸, etc., have been used. Studies of oxygen evolution have also been carried out on oxides both pure as well as mixed ones possessing metallic as well as semiconducting properties⁹⁻¹¹. Among these mixed oxides especially of spinel or perovskite-type structures have been considered¹² to be very promising, as they are low cost, easily available and have outstanding corrosion stability in strong base.

The spinel group of metal oxides have the general composition $MM'O_4$, where M and M' are metal ions. In the spinel structures, one of the cations is located in an octahedral site. Oxygen anions are arranged in f.c.c. packing arrangement. A number of oxides of this group have been investigated for oxygen evolution reaction in KOH solution and were extensively reviewed by Tarasevich and Efremov¹⁰ and O'Sullivan and Calvo¹². They were generally prepared by simple conventional thermal decomposition methods. Transition metal spinel oxides, thus prepared, have, in fact, low conductivity and low specific surface area. To enhance the surface area, several new methods, such as co-precipitation, freeze-drying etc. were also employed. In some cases, the electrical conductivity was enhanced by producing the oxide in the form of thin films on conductive supports by an oxide-painting^{14,15} or a solution coating method^{16,17}. The use of conducting carriers as well as promoters¹⁵ have also been made to raise the oxide conductivity.

The basic structures of perovskite-type oxides may be represented as ABO_3 , where A is a large cation such as, lanthanide element and B is a transition metal cation. The electrocatalytic activity of the oxide is greatly modified by introducing the partial substitution of either A with another similar type to give $A_{1-x}A_x'BO_3$ or B ion with another similar type to give $AB_{1-x}B_x'O_3$. Although the ideal structure of perovskite oxide is cubic, deviations from this structure occur due to variation in ionic radii of the constituent ions. Some perovskite oxides, e.g. $LaNiO_3$, $LaCoO_3$, $La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO_3$, $SrFeO_3$, $La_{1-x}Sr_xMnO_3$, etc., have already been investigated for oxygen evolution

in alkaline solution^{12,18,19}. These oxides were generally prepared by high temperature solid state reactions or thermal decomposition method. The oxide electrodes studied were in the form of pellets.

A survey of literature reveals that the method, starting materials and experimental conditions used in the synthesis of the oxides have a strong influence²⁰ on their textural characteristics and hence the interfacial properties of the oxides used in electrocatalysis. The LaNiO_3 electrode prepared by the hydroxide co-precipitation method, as reported¹⁹ by Bockris and Otagawa, exhibited the highest activity among the perovskite-electrodes. It showed many times greater activity than the same oxide prepared by a conventional ceramic method. Tseung *et al.*²¹ demonstrated that the teflon-bonded NiCo_2O_4 electrode gave a current density of 1.0 A cm^{-2} at 70° in 5 N KOH at 1.6 V vs DHE, but when a thin layer of NiCo_2O_4 was formed on the electrode surface by the thermal decomposition of nickel-cobalt nitrates, the performance of the electrode improved to 2 A cm^{-2} .

In order to increase the electrical conductivity and homogeneity we have synthesised mixed oxides catalysts, such as Co_3O_4 , NiCo_2O_4 , LaNiO_3 , $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{-Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ in the film forms on conductive supports. The methods of spray pyrolysis and also sequential coating of mixed metal nitrates were used in the film preparation. The former procedure is relatively low cost and quite suitable to limit the amount of materials. To produce large surface area oxides, a low temperature synthesis, malic acid-aided method was also used, particularly for the preparation of cobaltates. We have also obtained thin films of Ni and Ni-Fe alloys on mild steels by the method of electro-deposition. These catalytic films have been investigated²²⁻³⁰ in detail for their physicochemical and electrochemical surface properties in relation to oxygen evolution reaction.

This report presents the summarised results of the electrochemical investigations made on different catalytic films towards oxygen evolution.

Results and Discussion

Cyclic voltammetry : With the exception of the $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ films on Pt or Ti and the sprayed Co_3O_4 film on Ni, all the electrocatalysts prepared *in situ* exhibited an anodic and a corresponding cathodic peak before O_2 evolution in their corresponding cyclic voltammograms, recorded between 0 and 0.7 V (Hg/HgO), at any scan rate between 10 and 100 mV s^{-1} in 1 M KOH at 25° . Voltammograms for the sprayed Co_3O_4 films on Ni showed two anodic and corresponding two cathodic peaks, on contrary, the layered films of the same oxide on Ni exhibited a single anodic and a corresponding cathodic peak. Also, similar sprayed films of Co_3O_4 on substrates other than Ni indicated^{22,23} a single anodic and a corresponding cathodic peak only. On the other hand, cyclic voltammetry of the $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ film on Pt and Ti in 1 M KOH did not indicate any redox peak prior to the onset of oxygen evolution, whereas the same oxide film on Ni showed a pair of the redox peaks. Typical cyclic voltammograms for $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{-Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ and Co_3O_4 film electrodes are shown in Figs. 1-3. Values of

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of Co_3O_4 films on Ni and Fe substrates at a potential scan of 20 mV s^{-1} in 1 M KOH (25°); oxide loadings : (O) 6.8 , (●) 4.2 , (Δ) 4.4 and (▲) 4.2 mg cm^{-2} .

the anodic peak potential (E_{pa}), the cathodic peak potential (E_{pc}), the peak separation potential (ΔE_p), and the formal redox potential [$E^0 = (E_{pa} + E_{pc})/2$] were estimated in each case and are presented in Table 1.

In the case of Co_3O_4 , the redox peaks ($E_{pa} = 512\text{--}554 \text{ mV}$), $E_{pc} = (490\text{--}510 \text{ mV})$ observed

TABLE I—RESULTS OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRY OF DIFFERENT ELECTROCATALYSTS IN 1 M KOH AT 25°

Electrode*		Catalyst loading mg cm ⁻²	E_{pa} mV	E_{pc} mV	ΔE_p mV	E^0 mV
		$S = 20 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$				
Glass/CdO/Co ₃ O ₄	(s)	—	526	496	29	510
Ti/Co ₃ O ₄	(s)	—	545	510	35	527
Ni/Co ₃ O ₄	(s)	6.8	547	498, 333	49	522
Ni/Co ₃ O ₄	(l)	4.2	540	510	30	525
Fe/Co ₃ O ₄	(s)	4.2	554	506	48	530
Fe/Co ₃ O ₄	(l)	4.4	512	490	22	501
Glass/CdO/NiCo ₂ O ₄	(s)	—	510	315	195	412
Ti/NiCo ₂ O ₄	(s)	—	475	360	115	417
Ni/NiCo ₂ O ₄	(s)	0.5	490	320	170	405
Pt/LaNiO ₃	(s)	—	515	410	105	462
Pt/LaNiO ₃	(l)	9.0	515	435	80	475
Ni/LaNiO ₃	(l)	6.2	495	415	81	455
		$S = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$				
Ni/LaCoO ₃	(mal)	3.0	480	300	180	390
Ni/La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃	(mal)	3.0	460	310	150	385
Ni/La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃	(nit)	—	440	300	140	370
Pt/La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃	(mal)	—	—	No redox peaks were observed		
Ni/La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} CoO ₃	(mal)	—	470	330	140	400
Ti/La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃	(mal)	—	—	No redox peaks were observed		
		$S = 20 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$				
AISI 302	(comm)	—	490	380	110	435
AISI 304	(comm)	—	512	385	127	448
AISI 321	(comm)	—	535	410	127	448
82.1Ni-17.9Fe	(el)	—	515	385	130	450
81 Ni-19 Fe	(el)	—	515	410	105	462
75.2Ni-24.8Fe	(el)	—	510	415	95	462
71.5Ni-28.5Fe	(el)	—	530	410	120	470
84.4Ni-15.6Fe	(el)	—	510	405	105	457

* s : spray, l : layer, mal : malic acid-aided, nit : nitrates decomposition, comm : commercial, el : electrodeposited.

have been attributed^{22,23} to the formation of the redox couple, $\text{Co}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Co}^{\text{III}}$, on the electrode surface during potential cycling conditions, while that on other catalyst surfaces, the redox couple, $\text{Ni}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ ²⁷⁻³⁰. The redox peaks obtained on the $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ film on Ni were presumably due to the dispersion of nickel ions into the oxide film during the oxide annealing process, which is quite evident from the cyclic voltammograms of the catalytic film of the same oxide on Pt or Ti. The first anodic and the corresponding cathodic peak ($E_{pa} \sim 465$, $E_{pc} \sim 333$ mV) observed in the voltammogram for the $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ electrode also indicate the dispersion of nickel ions into the oxide film.

The study of the effect of scan rate on cyclic voltammograms (i_p vs scan rate and i_p vs

$\sqrt{\text{scan rate}}$) indicated that the formation of the redox couple at each oxide electrode, regardless of their nature, is diffusion-controlled.

It is noteworthy that the peaks obtained on LaNiO_3 were quite sharp. The similar sharply defined peaks have, to our knowledge, never been reported with massive pellets of LaNiO_3 . Further, in the case of stainless steels, the redox peaks for the $\text{Ni}^{\text{III}}-\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ reaction clearly demonstrated the presence of nickel ions on the steel surface, which is, in fact, known to be enveloped essentially by a thin corrosion resistant film of Cr_2O_3 . It seems that the Cr_2O_3 lattice contains some nickel ions also.

The observation of Figs. 1-2 and Table 1 further shows that the oxygen evolution takes

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ films on Ni at a potential scan of 20 mV s^{-1} in 1 M KOH (25°): (A) LaCoO_3 , (B) $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{CoO}_3$ and (C) $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{CoO}_3$.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{CoO}_3$ films on Pt and Ti substrates at a potential scan of 10 mV s^{-1} in 1 M KOH (25°): (D) $\text{Pt/La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{CoO}_3$ and (E) $\text{Ti/La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{CoO}_3$.

TABLE 2—ELECTRODE KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR OXYGEN EVOLUTION ON DIFFERENT ELECTROCATALYSTS IN 1 M KOH AT 25°

Electrode	Catalyst loading mg cm^{-2}	Resistance of the electrode (R) Ω	Roughness factor	Reaction order ρ_{OH^-}	Tafel slope mV decade^{-1}	η (mV)	
						10 mA cm^{-2}	100 mA cm^{-2}
G/CdO/Co ₃ O ₄ (s)	—	30	5	1.3	60	665 ^a	—
Ti/Co ₃ O ₄ (s)	—	8	9	2	50	623 ^b	—
Ni/Co ₃ O ₄ (s)	6.8	0.3	450	1.6	60	360	422
Ni/Co ₃ O ₄ (l)	4.2	0.5	244	1.2	53	350	406
Fe/Co ₃ O ₄ (s)	2.1	2	322	1.4	60	329	398
Fe/Co ₃ O ₄ (l)	4.4	0.5	280	1.2	55	375	445
G/CdO/NiCo ₂ O ₄ (s)	—	20	55	1.3	55	522	—
Ti/NiCo ₂ O ₄ (s)	—	12	58	2	67	479	—
Ni/NiCo ₂ O ₄ (s)	0.5	25.5	25.5	1.7	42	339	457
Pt/LaNiO ₃ (s)	—	2	170	2.2	45	337	387
Pt/LaNiO ₃ (l)	9.0	2	470	1.2	65	330	410
Ni/LaNiO ₃ (l)	6.17	0.4	666	1.2	64	340	457
Ni/LaCoO ₃ (mal)	3	0.9	265	1.2	60	325	401
Ni/La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃ (mal)	3.0	0.7	563	1.1	63	310	387
Ni/La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃ (nit)	3.0	0.6	406	1.1	61	330	405
Pt/La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃ (mal)	3.0	1.1	360	1.2	59	338	430
Ni/La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} CoO ₃ (mal)	3	0.7	442	1.1	60	325	401
AISI 302	—	—	—	1.8	31–33	292	380
AISI 304	—	—	—	2.1	28–30	323	451
AISI 321	—	—	—	1.9	32–35	340	451
82.1 Ni–17.9 Fe (el)	—	2.4	—	2	35	264	310

^a1.7 M KOH. ^b2 M KOH.

place on the oxidised cobalt or nickel sites in the catalytic film, as the anodic redox peak is followed by oxygen evolution.

Roughness factors : To determine the electrochemically active area of the oxide electrodes, cyclic voltammograms of each electrode in 1 M KOH were recorded at varying scan rates in the small potential region (0–50 mV) near open-circuit potential. The typical cyclic voltammograms for $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{CoO}_3$ are shown in Fig. 4. The double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) values were

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of the $\text{Ni}/\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{CoO}_3$ electrode in the potential range of 0–0.05 V at varying scan-rates in 1 M KOH (25°).

determined from the slope of linear plot, i_{cap} vs scan rate, where i_{cap} is the charging current measured at the middle of the scan range (i.e. 25 mV). Values of the roughness factor for each oxide film electrode were calculated by assuming a C_{dl} of $60 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ for a smooth oxide surface. Depending upon the nature of supports and of the oxide, varying values of the roughness factor were obtained as shown in Table 2. The results showed that the roughness factor was the highest for the oxide film on Ni.

The effect of the oxide loading on the electrochemically active area of the film in the

case of the LaNiO_3 film and the Co_3O_4 film on Ni has also been investigated. The results showed that as the oxide loading is increased, the electrochemically active area increases almost linearly at the beginning and approaches a limiting value thereafter (Fig. 5). This complex behaviour

Fig. 5 The effect of oxide loadings on the roughness factor

may be due to the fact that at low loadings almost entire crystallites come in contact with the electrolyte but when loading exceeds a certain critical value, some crystallites get excluded from the contact with the solution and that the number of such crystallites increases with increasing the oxide loading^{30,32}.

Tafel plots : The electrocatalytic activity of different electrocatalysts towards oxygen evolution were investigated by the Tafel polarisation technique in 1 M KOH at 25° and the results are summarised in Table 2. Table 2 demonstrates that the nature of supports has a strong influence on the electrocatalytic activity of the films.

The catalytic films of Co_3O_4 on Ni and Fe were found to be much more active than the same films on glass/CdO or Ti supports. The oxygen overpotential at 10 mA cm^{-2} in 1 M KOH was approximately 160 mV less at the Co_3O_4 film on Ni compared to the film of same oxide on Ti. The sprayed NiCo_2O_4 film on Ni also gave 140–180 mV lower oxygen overpotential

TABLE 3—ELECTROCATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF THE CATALYTIC FILM ELECTRODES IN 30 w/o KOH

Electrode	Catalyst loading mg cm ⁻²	η (V)				
		25°			70°	
		0.1	0.3	0.5	0.5	1.0
		i(A cm ⁻²)				
Ni/La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃	3.0	0.340	0.392	0.420	0.305	0.340
Ni/Co ₃ O ₄ (layer)	4.2	0.377	0.405	0.422	0.364	0.407
Ni/Co ₃ O ₄ (spray)	6.8	0.390	0.427	0.447	0.365	0.389
Fe/Co ₃ O ₄ (layer)	4.4	0.376	0.445	0.466	0.365	0.389
Fe/Co ₃ O ₄ (spray)	4.2	0.371	0.412	0.435	0.340	0.397
Ni/LaNiO ₃ (layer)	6.2	0.380	0.490	0.520	0.340	0.370
Pt/LaNiO ₃ (spray)	—	0.280	—	—	—	—
Pt/LaNiO ₃ (layer)	9.0	0.360	—	—	—	—
Mild steel/Ni-17.9%Fe	—	0.280	—	—	—	—

than the similar films on other supports. On the other hand, the sprayed LaNiO₃ film on Pt was electrocatalytically more active than the LaNiO₃ film on Ni. It produced ~ 70 mV lower oxygen overpotential at 100 mA cm⁻² in 1 M KOH than the Ni/LaNiO₃ electrode. Further, the La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}CoO₃ film on Ni showed slightly higher activity for oxygen evolution than that on Pt.

In order to increase the efficiency of the traditional nickel anode we have also prepared a number of electrodeposited films of Ni-Fe alloys of varying compositions (15.6–28.5%). Of these, the alloy with 17.9% Fe showed remarkably high efficiency for oxygen evolutions. The overpotential for oxygen evolution at this electrode was ~ 300 mV lower, at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻² in 1 M KOH at 25°, than the pure nickel anode³³. It is worth mentioning that the electrocatalytic activity of the Ni-17.9 Fe electrode was more or less equal to the active LaNiO₃ electrode, which was prepared by Bockris and Otagawa¹⁹ following the method of hydroxide coprecipitation. The latter electrode is presently considered as one of the best oxygen anodes. Commercial stainless steels were also observed to be more active than Ni³³.

Some of the electrodes, whose performance were reasonably high in 1 M KOH have further been tested in commercial alkaline solutions (30 w/o KOH) and the results are shown in Table 3. Table 3 shows that the performance of the Pt/LaNiO₃ and mild steel/Ni-17.9 Fe electrodes is better in 30 w/o KOH also (25°) up to a

current density of 100 mA cm⁻². The electrocatalytic activities of these electrodes are yet to be examined for a higher current density applications. The Fe/Co₃O₄ electrodes with loadings < 0.3 mg cm⁻² were observed to be not suitable for the use of a current density greater than 500 mA cm⁻² as they showed fluctuations in the current density. However, the electrodes, Ni/La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}CoO₃, Ni/Co₃O₄ and Ni/LaNiO₃ did not indicate any fluctuation in the whole range of current density recorded at both the temperatures 25 and 70°. It was observed that at 70°, in commercial alkaline solution, La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}CoO₃ prepared by the malic acid-aided method was much more active than the other perovskite film electrodes, such as LaNiO₃, La_{0.5}Sr_{0.5}Co_{0.8}Ni_{0.2}O₃ and La_{0.5}Ba_{0.5}CoO₃, obtained by nitrate decomposition method³⁴. The La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}CoO₃ electrode produced an overpotential of ~ 310 mV in 30 w/o KOH at 70°, while other electrodes gave ~ 280 mV in 10 M (~40 w/o KOH) at 100°. The performance of the cobaltate electrode appears to be superior also to other oxide coated electrodes reported in literature^{35,36}. The Ni/LaNiO₃ electrode also seems to be better for a current density application of 1 A cm⁻² or so at 70°.

Mechanism of oxygen evolution : Studies of oxygen evolution on different catalytic films indicate that the nature of both the catalytic film as well as of the support influences the mechanistic paths of the oxygen evolution reaction. Based on the results, the following two reaction Schemes 1 and 2 for oxygen evolution have been proposed.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

where S (= Co^{IV} or Ni^{III}), an active site on the electrode surface.

Considering step (2) as the rate-determining, the electrolysis current (*i*) under Langmuir adsorption conditions can be written as

$$i = n F k_2 K_1 C_{OH^-}^2 \exp(FE/RT) \quad (8)$$

where, $K_1 (= k_1/k_{-1})$ is the adsorption-desorption equilibrium constant for the process¹. The other terms have their usual significance. Equation (8) gives a Tafel slope of ~ 60 mV decade⁻¹ and second order kinetics in OH⁻ concentration. This explains the results obtained on the sprayed Co₃O₄ and NiCo₂O₄ films on Ti at lower concentration of KOH (< 3 M).

If step (3) (Scheme 1) is the rate-determining, the value of net electrolysis current under low adsorption conditions can be given as

$$i = n F k_3 K_1 K_2 C_{OH^-}^2 \exp\left(\frac{3FE}{2RT}\right) \text{ assuming } \beta = 1/2 \quad (9)$$

This shows second order kinetics in OH⁻ concentration and the Tafel slope of ~ 40 mV decade⁻¹. Similar values of the Tafel parameters were also found on sprayed cobaltite films on Ti (in KOH solution > 3 M), sprayed NiCo₂O₄ films on Ni, sprayed LaNiO₃ films on Pt and on Ni-Fe alloys.

However, under Temkin adsorption conditions (0.2 < θ_T < 0.8, where, θ_T = θ_{OH⁻} + θ_{OH} + θ_{H₂O₂}) the rate-determining step (3) gives the electrolysis current,

$$i = n F k_3 K_2 \theta_{OH^-} C_{OH^-} \exp\left(\frac{3FE}{RT}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\alpha r \theta_T}{RT}\right) \quad (10)$$

where α is another symmetry factor and $K_2 (= k_2/k_{-2})$ is the equilibrium constant for the reaction (2). *r* is coefficient determining the variation of the heat of adsorption with θ_T, the value of which can be computed from the relation,

$$\frac{\theta_T}{RT} = \ln K_1 C_{OH^-} + \frac{FE}{RT} \quad (11)$$

considering the θ_{OH} is relatively invariant under intermediate coverage conditions, equations (10) and 11 result the Tafel slope and the reaction order with respect to OH⁻ concentration as near 2.3 RT/F (~ 60 mV decade⁻¹) and 1.5, respectively, α and β each being 1/2. Approximately the same values of the Tafel slope and the reaction order were observed on sprayed Co₃O₄ and NiCo₂O₄ films on glass/CdO, layered LaNiO₃ films on Pt and Ni substrates and La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃ films on Ni and Pt substrates.

The current density for oxygen evolution (under low adsorption conditions) can be given from Scheme 2 as

$$i = n F k_2 K_1^2 C_{OH^-}^2 \exp\left(\frac{2FE}{RT}\right) \quad (12)$$

Thus, the rate equation (12) explains the observed electrode kinetic parameters for oxygen evolution on different stainless steels.

Experimental

Thin films of Co₃O₄, NiCo₂O₄ and LaNiO₃ and of Ni-Fe alloys were prepared by different methods as already described in our previous publications²²⁻³⁰. The synthesis of LaCoO₃, La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}CoO₃, and La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}CoO₃ were carried out by malic acid-aided method, the details of which are given in Ref. 31. The electrical connection to the oxide film was taken from the metal surface (with conductive silver paste) which was not used for the film preparation. Only in the case of the Co₃O₄ (or NiCo₂O₄) film on glass/CdO, the electrical connection was made with the oxide surface itself. Only 1 (or 0.5) cm² surface of the oxide film was used for the study and the remaining surface was covered with Araldite.

Electrochemical studies were carried out in a conventional three-electrode single compartment Pyrex glass cell using an electrochemical impedance system (model 388, EG & G PARC), a bi-potentiostat (model RDE4, Pine Instrument Company, U.S.A.) or a PGS 81 potentiogalvanoscanner (Wenking model).

The surface morphology of the films as obtained on conductive supports was examined by a scanning electron microscope (Jeol). The formation of the oxide concerned was checked by powder X-ray diffraction technique.

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